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The α -Inverse Sum Indeg Index and Some Hamiltonian Properties of Graphs

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. The α -inverse sum indeg index of a graph G is defined as $\sum_{uv \in E} \frac{d^\alpha(u)d^\alpha(v)}{d^\alpha(u)+d^\alpha(v)}$, where $\alpha > 0$ is a real number and $d(u)$ and $d(v)$ denote the degrees of vertices u and v in G , respectively. In this note, we present an upper bound for the α -inverse sum indeg index of a graph and sufficient conditions involving the α -inverse sum indeg index for some Hamiltonian properties of graphs.

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traceable graph

1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notations and terminologies not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G =$

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$(V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use δ and Δ to denote the minimum degree and maximum degree of G , respectively. The complement of a graph G is denoted by G^c . We use $G[S]$ denotes a subgraph induced by a subset S of $V(G)$. A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E(X, Y) := \{e : e = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y\}$. We use $G_1 \vee G_2$ to denote the the join of two disjoint graphs G_1 and G_2 . The complete graph of order p is denoted by K_p . A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamiltonian cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamiltonian path.

A variety of topological indexes for graphs such as Wiener index [6], Randić index [4], and the first Zagreb index [3] have been introduced. In 2010, Vukičević and Gašperov in [5] introduced the inverse sum indeg index of a graph G , denoted $ISI(G)$, which is defined as

$$ISI(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} \frac{d(u)d(v)}{d(u) + d(v)}.$$

Motivated by the definition of $ISI(G)$, we introduce the α -inverse sum indeg index of a graph, denoted $ISI_\alpha(G)$, which is defined

$$ISI_\alpha(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} \frac{d^\alpha(u)d^\alpha(v)}{d^\alpha(u) + d^\alpha(v)},$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is a real number. Obviously, $ISI_\alpha(G)$ becomes $ISI(G)$ when $\alpha = 1$. In this note, we present an upper bound for the α -inverse sum indeg index of a graph and sufficient conditions involving the α -inverse sum indeg index for Hamiltonian graphs and traceable graphs. The main results are as follows.

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Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and $\delta \geq 1$. Then

$$ISI_\alpha(G) \leq \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-\beta)^\alpha\beta(n-\beta)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-\beta)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-\beta)(n-\beta-1)}{4}$$

with equality if and only if G is $K_\beta^c \vee K_{n-\beta}$.

Theorem 2. Let G be a graph k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. If

$$ISI_\alpha(G) \geq \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-1)^\alpha(k+1)(n-k-1)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-k-1)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-1)(n-k-2)}{4},$$

then G is Hamiltonian or G is $K_{k+1}^c \vee K_k$.

Theorem 3. Let G be a graph k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph with n vertices. If

$$ISI_\alpha(G) \geq \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)^\alpha(k+2)(n-k-2)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-k-2)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)(n-k-3)}{4},$$

then G is traceable or G is $K_{k+2}^c \vee K_k$.

2 Lemmas

We will use the following results as our lemmas.

Lemma 1 [2]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order $n \geq 3$. If $\beta \leq k$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 2 [2]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order n . If $\beta \leq k+1$, then G is traceable.

3 Proofs

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Proof of Theorem 1. Suppose G is a graph with n vertices and $\delta \geq 1$. Let I be an independent set such that $|I| = \beta$. Then $1 \leq \beta \leq n - 1$ and $1 \leq n - \beta \leq n - 1$. Clearly, $d(x) \leq n - \beta$ for each $x \in I$ and $d(y) \leq \Delta$ for each $y \in V - I$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in I, v \in V-I} \frac{d^\alpha(u)d^\alpha(v)}{d^\alpha(u) + d^\alpha(v)} \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in I, v \in V-I} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{d^\alpha(u)} + \frac{1}{d^\alpha(v)}} \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in I, v \in V-I} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{d^\alpha(u)} + \frac{1}{d^\alpha(v)}} \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in I, v \in V-I} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{(n-\beta)^\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Delta^\alpha}} \\ &= \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-\beta)^\alpha \beta(n-\beta)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-\beta)^\alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

We further have

$$\begin{aligned} S_2 &:= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in V-I, v \in V-I, u \neq v} \frac{d^\alpha(u)d^\alpha(v)}{d^\alpha(u) + d^\alpha(v)} \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in V-I, v \in V-I, u \neq v} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{d^\alpha(u)} + \frac{1}{d^\alpha(v)}} \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in V-I, v \in V-I, u \neq v} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{d^\alpha(u)} + \frac{1}{d^\alpha(v)}} \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in V-I, v \in V-I, u \neq v} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\Delta^\alpha} + \frac{1}{\Delta^\alpha}} \\ &= \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-\beta)(n-\beta-1)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$ISI(G)_\alpha(G) = \sum_{uv \in E} \frac{d^\alpha(u)d^\alpha(v)}{d^\alpha(u) + d^\alpha(v)} = S_1 + S_2$$

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$$\leq \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - \beta)^\alpha \beta(n - \beta)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n - \beta)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{4}.$$

If

$$ISI_\alpha(G) = \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - \beta)^\alpha \beta(n - \beta)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n - \beta)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{4},$$

In reviewing all the proofs above, we have that $d(x) = n - \beta$ for each $x \in I$ and thereby $xy \in E$ for each $x \in I$ and each $y \in V - I$, $d(y) = \Delta$ for each $y \in V - I$, and $G[V - I]$ is complete. Therefore G is $K_\beta^c \vee K_{n-\beta}$.

If G is $K_\beta^c \vee K_{n-\beta}$, a simple computation yields

$$ISI_\alpha(G) = \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - \beta)^\alpha \beta(n - \beta)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n - \beta)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{4}.$$

Hence we complete the proof of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices satisfying the conditions in Theorem 2. Suppose G is not Hamiltonian. Then Lemma 1 implies that $\beta \geq k + 1$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 1 \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq n/2$ and G is Hamiltonian. Let $I_1 := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1}\}$ is an independent set in G . Following the proof of Theorem 1, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - k - 1)^\alpha(k + 1)(n - k - 1)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n - k - 1)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - k - 1)(n - k - 2)}{4} \\ & \leq ISI_\alpha(G) \leq \\ & \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - k - 1)^\alpha(k + 1)(n - k - 1)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n - k - 1)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - k - 1)(n - k - 2)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} ISI_\alpha(G) &= \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - k - 1)^\alpha(k + 1)(n - k - 1)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n - k - 1)^\alpha} \\ & \quad + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n - k - 1)(n - k - 2)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x) = n - k - 1$ for each $x \in I$ and thereby $xy \in E$ for each $x \in I$ and each $y \in V - I$, $d(y) = \Delta$ for each $y \in V - I$, and $G[V - I]$ is complete.

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Thus G is $K_{k+1}^c \vee K_{n-k-1}$. Since $n \geq 2k + 1$, we have that $|V - I| \geq k$. If $|V - I| \geq (k + 1)$, then G is Hamiltonian, a contradiction. Thus $|V - I| = k$ and G is $K_{k+1}^c \vee K_k$. Hence we complete the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 3. If $n = 1$ or $n = 2$, then it is trivial that G is traceable. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices satisfying the conditions in Theorem 3. Suppose G is not traceable. Then Lemma 2 implies that $\beta \geq k + 2$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 2 \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq (n - 1)/2$ and G is traceable. Let $I_1 := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+2}\}$ is an independent set in G . Following the proof of Theorem 1, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)^\alpha(k+2)(n-k-2)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-k-2)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)(n-k-3)}{4} \\ & \leq ISI_\alpha(G) \leq \\ & \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)^\alpha(k+2)(n-k-2)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-k-2)^\alpha} + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)(n-k-3)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} ISI_\alpha(G) &= \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)^\alpha(k+2)(n-k-2)}{\Delta^\alpha + (n-k-2)^\alpha} \\ & \quad + \frac{\Delta^\alpha(n-k-2)(n-k-3)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x) = n - k - 2$ for each $x \in I$ and thereby $xy \in E$ for each $x \in I$ and each $y \in V - I$, $d(y) = \Delta$ for each $y \in V - I$, and $G[V - I]$ is complete. Thus G is $K_{k+2}^c \vee K_{n-k-2}$. Since $n \geq 2k + 2$, we have that $|V - I| \geq k$. If $|V - I| \geq (k + 1)$, then G is traceable, a contradiction. Thus $|V - I| = k$ and G is $K_{k+2}^c \vee K_k$. Hence we complete the proof of Theorem 3.

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